

Mapping the state of neuroscientific software - a vision for collaboration beyond single institutes or labs

A perspective by Software Engineers from [The International Brain Lab](#), [The Allen Institute for Neural Dynamics](#) and the [Neuroinformatics Unit](#).

Software to acquire, process, analyse and visualize data underpins modern neuroscience. As a growing experimental toolbox produces data of increasing complexity and size to understand the brain, the software tools need to keep pace with these developments. It should be easy to compare, reuse, adapt, combine and improve tools to suit novel experiments. However, despite existing community efforts to allow this, the software ecosystem remains fragmented.

This fragmentation means that it is difficult to compare the results of e.g. different spike-sorting or image registration tools on the same data because they differ in the assumptions they make, the platforms they use, the software libraries (and their versions) they depend on and computational expertise they require. Similarly, it is challenging to run the same algorithm on different data, because the software relies on the data being in a specific format. This results in many duplicate implementations of the same algorithm, often at the level of an individual lab, wasting resources.

As members of [Research Software Engineering teams](#) of leading neuroscience institutes we are uniquely placed (and therefore feel a particularly strong responsibility) to drive improvements in the cohesion of neuroscience software for everyone. In this article, we present our perspective on the current state of this ecosystem for different kinds of neuroscientific data, and the vision we are working towards, together. We stress that we aim to do this in a community-driven way, and encourage anyone interested to get involved with our efforts. The [Neuroinformatics Unit's chat platform](#) is a good way to introduce yourself and engage with others.

To work towards a less fragmented, more interoperable software landscape, we identify current limitations of software available to work with specific data modalities, and how we plan to address them, below. Overall, we propose that the best way to improve the neuroscientific software ecosystem lies mainly in work towards general-purpose, interoperable and easily extensible *frameworks* (rather than restricting individual tools, algorithms or acquisition systems). This approach allows researchers to mix and match, tweak and compare existing and custom tools, as well as integrating new tools as they are made, while avoiding duplication of efforts. Further benefits include an increase in transparency and reproducibility of scientific results, leading to better science.

Neurophysiological timeseries

For electrophysiological data, [SpikelInterface](#) has widespread community adoption. Its success is rooted in providing a common framework for running a number of different preprocessing, spike-sorting, and postprocessing algorithms—rendering them easily interchangeable. Current challenges lie in the difficulty of assessing the quality of raw

data and the performance of a heterogeneous set of processing steps. We initially suggest tackling this by standardising quality control methods and creating a benchmark of raw and preprocessed data snippets. We also aim to converge on a single containerised pipeline that will automatically generate quality-control outputs.

For multiphoton imaging applications, many scientists use [suite2p](#) and [CalmAn](#). While both are excellent tools for specific imaging conditions, they are not designed to be mutually interoperable or particularly modular. This means combining processing steps from these pipelines with custom steps is not straightforward. Inspired by the SpikeInterface idea, we therefore plan to work towards a [standardised framework](#) that can wrap multiphoton imaging steps (like motion correction or source extraction) — in the first instance, we will discuss metadata standards for each of these steps.

The maturity of the software ecosystem supporting fibre photometry data lags behind multiphoton imaging and electrophysiological probe applications. Initial collaborative work will focus on adopting shared quality control tools and metadata as well as data sharing, before formulating a way forward for analysis tools.

Behavioural videos

The community is considering coalescing around [movement](#) as a unified community toolbox to analyse outputs of the heterogeneous pose estimation tools available (e.g. [SLEAP](#), [DeepLabCut](#), [LightningPose](#)). With the aim of facilitating better comparisons of pose estimation and point-tracking tools for neuroscientific applications, we are working on a cross-institutional, publicly available benchmarking dataset. This will include a diverse set of videos with corresponding proof-read ground truth and pre-computed model results. We plan to evaluate various baseline models on this dataset and provide functionality to easily extend both the dataset and the baseline models. We believe this standardisation will have the further benefit of buy-in from a more generalist computer vision community.

Histological data

Neuroanatomical atlases provide registration targets to allow aligning histological data from multiple samples, even across studies, to the same coordinate space, e.g. the [Allen Common Coordinate Framework](#). The [BrainGlobe Initiative](#) (and in particular its Atlas API) have largely standardised programmatic access to a number of publicly available atlases from multiple species, and we are now working jointly towards storing these in a more web-accessible and flexible data format. We hope that we can enable standardised programmatic access to atlas-aligned data in the longer term.

General software requirements

Beyond tools aimed at any specific type of neuroscientific data, we identify a number of areas where general software needs for neuroscientists exist. We should aim for all our software tools to be accessible with little or no computational knowledge, to come with robust workflow management tools, and to run on local machines, institutional compute clusters and public cloud. Coordination on metadata and quality control metrics would also be highly beneficial.

Conclusion

As we embark on this journey together, we invite researchers and engineers to participate in the open-source ecosystem and to help build neuroscientific software that benefits the entire community. This requires a wide range of contributions — from code, documentation, and community management to scientific guidance, technical expertise, and new ideas. We will establish shared and transparent governance and attribution mechanisms to recognise all such contributions, and we will continue advocating for funders and career panels to do the same. This vision depends on collaboration beyond our own groups and on fully acknowledging the collective effort behind better neuroscientific software.

This text is the result of discussions from a two-day workshop held in Portugal in October 2025. If you'd like to get involved, get [in touch via Zulip](#).

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